

ON THE IMPORTANCE OF THOROUGH IN SILICO DRUG-COATED BALLOON REPLICAS TO SIMULATE COATING TRANSFER

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1. Introduction

Drug-Coated Balloons (DCBs) provide a promising minimally invasive solution to treat stenotic arteries, by advocating the leave-nothing-behind strategy and by offering the potential to deliver the drug-coating homogeneously on the lesion. This should act as a long-term, homogeneous, local drug source. However, recent animal studies revealed limited coating transfer [1]. Moreover, *in vitro* studies of DCBs suggested the Contact Pressure (CP) between the balloon and the endothelium to be the leading cause of the transfer [2]. Considering the above, this work suggests a detailed angioplasty balloon computational model aiming to predict the spatial distribution of CP during a DCB angioplasty.

2. Materials and Methods

A finite element model of an angioplasty balloon was implemented, taking into account the realistic, longitudinal non-uniform wall thickness and folding process. The folded balloon was then expanded in idealized human femoral artery models (cylinders with suitable wall stiffness), using explicit, quasi-static simulations. Various conditions were investigated (Table 1), to evaluate the CP spatial distribution for a wide range of Inflation Pressures (IPs).

Conditions	Value 1	Value 2	Value 3
Oversizing (%)	15	25	40
Length (mm)	20	40	100
Friction	0	0.3	0.8
Positioning	Concentric	Eccentric	Inclined
Artery stiffness	Healthy	Stiffening 1	Stiffening 2

Table 1: Balloon expansion simulation conditions.

3. Results

Figure 1 represents a 2D colour map of the CP on the arterial wall. The CP after full expansion (for IPs equal to 1.1-1.5 MPa) of the balloon

catheter reveals one order of magnitude lower values with respect to the concurrent IP. Furthermore, the distribution is highly heterogeneous, because the initial irregular contact formed linearly patterned contact zones, while the balloon's non-uniform thickness creates higher CP in the vessel's central part.

Figure 1: CP values among different IP maps. The x-axis represents the length and the y-axis the circumference.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

Conclusively, this study disclosed the highly irregular contact between the balloon and the artery, which is completely justified by the balloon's features, since a cylindrical geometry was adopted for the artery. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first evidence and interpretation of systematic, heterogeneous CP developed during angioplasty, that could explain the animal studies observation with limited coating transfer.

5. References

1. A. R. Tzafiriri et al., Biomaterials, vol. 260, p. 120337, Nov. 2020
2. G. H. Chang et al. Sci Rep, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 6839, Dec. 2019

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